

OCEAN:ICE News – February 2024

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome to the February Edition of OCEAN:ICE News!

As winter winds down, we're thrilled to keep you updated on the latest from the world of OCEAN:ICE. This month's newsletter features highlights from the recent 1st OCEAN:ICE and Arctic PASSION policy briefing, engaging Climate Coffees, and our collaborative "Explain it in Two Ways" video series with PolarRES.

Get to know our featured researcher of the month, delve into the intriguing workshop on Anomalous Freshwater for Climate Models, mark your calendars for the upcoming OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting as well as stay informed about the upcoming Climate Coffees and where you can find OCEAN:ICE in action at various events.

Enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to bringing you more exciting news in March!

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

First OCEAN:ICE Policy Briefing

On the 24th of January [OCEAN:ICE](#) and [Arctic PASSION](#) held their 1st joint policy briefing “The Changing Poles: how Antarctic and Arctic science helps to inform and prepare the EU for changes in sea level rise and the global climate” at [European Parliament](#) and online. The briefing was opened by the host MEP Urmas Paet with the emphasis on the ‘issue of awareness’ and a statement ‘everything begins with knowledge’.

[Michael Karcher](#) from [Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research](#) delivered a presentation on [Arctic PASSION](#) project elaborating on the importance of the Arctic, knowledge-based decision-making and the needs in relation to Arctic change and Arctic observing.

[Ruth Mottram](#) from [Danish Meteorological Institute](#) and [Andrew Meijers](#) from [British Antarctic Survey](#) followed with a presentation on [OCEAN:ICE](#) stressing that ‘Polar regions are changing fast and they have consequences to us’.

After the presentations, the panel discussion took place with the participation of [Elisabetta Balzi](#), Clara Ganslandt and [Inuuteq Holm Olsen](#). The importance of acting and investment into polar research, the Arctic policy and the future, connecting the experience and infrastructure, sustainable development and closer cooperation, EU-Greenland relations, awareness raising, and the inclusion of local communities were discussed. [Elisabetta Balzi](#): ‘This is a very strategic and a very timely topic.’ Clara Ganslandt: ‘We need awareness raising on impacts of climate change, and that we have adequate political attention to it, we can assess it and ensure we have policies that are fit for purpose and we have adequate resources and are better prepared for the changes that will come’. [Inuuteq Holm Olsen](#): ‘We want to see better engagement of scientists with the local communities but also our research institutions’.

Important initiatives and projects, such as [EDITO - European Digital Twin Ocean](#), ‘Restore our Ocean and Waters’, [EU - PolarNet](#), [Arctic Hub](#), as well as events like EU Arctic Forum and Indigenous Peoples’ Dialogue, 14-15 May 2024 and European Polar Science Week, 3- 6 September 2024, [#eo4polar](#), were mentioned.

After the panel discussion, the Q&A session followed where the questions of commercial spaceports in the Arctic, collaboration with the US, the best ways of reaching the Greenlandic government and methods to raise the awareness were posed.

MEP Urmas Paet delivered closing remarks once again emphasising that the awareness should be raised, ‘attempt should be to show the larger picture and the impact’, preparations made, and science-based decisions taken.

You may access the report, the policy brief, and much more here → [OCEAN:ICE Policy Briefings and White Papers](#)

The Changing Poles: how Antarctic and Arctic science helps to inform and prepare the EU for changes in sea level rise and the global climate

Policy Brief
24 January 2024

Pictures provided by OCEAN:ICE and Arctic PASSION projects.

Arctic PASSION is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101003472

Ocean:ICE is co-funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement No. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

Keep an eye out for new OCEAN:ICE policy briefings which will be listed on our [Policy Briefings and White Papers](#) page.

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. Further down in the *Upcoming Climate Coffees* section you may find the busy lineup for upcoming Climate Coffees in 2024, and if you've missed any of the recent ones, don't worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

"Explain it in Two Ways" Video Series in Collaboration with PolarRES

We're thrilled to share an exciting collaboration between [OCEAN:ICE](#) and [PolarRES](#) – the launch of a new series, "[Explain it in Two Ways](#)"!

Five of our researchers are breaking down complex scientific processes for both the general public and scientific audience.

In the first [episode](#) @Ruth Mottram, OCEAN:ICE project coordinator, explains what **surface mass balance means** and its importance in Polar research. The second video explores the topic of [coupled climate models](#), featuring researchers Clara Lambin and Damien Maure. Last but not least, in the final episode of the series, @Ruth Price and @Ella Gilbert demystify the term: [mixed-phase clouds](#).

Visit OCEAN:ICE and PolarRES social media platforms to catch up with the episodes!

EXPLAIN IT IN TWO WAYS

VIDEO SERIES

 OCEAN:ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

 The PolarRES project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme call H2020-LC-CLA-2018-2019-2020 under grant agreement Nr. 101003590

Researcher in the Spotlight: Anna Olivé Abelló

We are continuing with our article series 'Researcher in the Spotlight'. Check out our latest feature on @Anna Olivé Abelló, a Post-Doctoral Researcher at the Institut des Géosciences de l'Environnement @Centre national de la recherche scientifique.

Read Anna's interview [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

Workshop on Anomalous Freshwater for Climate Models

On the 12th and 13th of February 2024, various members of the OCEAN:ICE community are going to participate in a virtual workshop, organised by [Dr. Gavin A. Schmidt](#), on defining ice sheet freshwater fluxes as boundary conditions for coupled climate models.

The workshop is going to draw together various scientists from multiple projects, initiatives, and groups. It will consist of pre-recorded talks from the invited speakers, interactive discussion groups, regional breakout groups, and three short global online video calls.

If you are interested in taking part in the workshop, you may register your interest [here](#).

Photo by [Andrew Meijers](#)

OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting, 23-25 September 2024, Copenhagen & online

Save the dates for the OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting, 23-25 September 2024, which will be kindly hosted by the Danish Meteorological Institute in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.

Stay [tuned](#) for more information.

Photo by [Nick Karvounis](#) on [Unsplash](#)

Upcoming Climate Coffees

[Emmanuele Russo](#) on [Increasing Intensity of Extreme Heatwaves: The Crucial Role of Metrics](#)

15 February 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CET).

Register [here](#).

The poster features the 'Climate Coffee' logo on the left, consisting of four wavy lines in blue, dark blue, light blue, and gold. To the right of the logo, the text 'Climate Coffee' is written in a large, bold, black sans-serif font. Further right is a cluster of dark brown coffee beans. Below the logo and title, the speaker's name 'Emmanuele Russo, ETH Zürich' is listed. The title of the talk is 'Increasing Intensity of Extreme Heatwaves: The Crucial Role of Metrics'. The date and time are '15 February 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET' and the format is 'Online'. At the bottom, there are logos for the Danish Meteorological Institute, ECRA, OCEAN:ICE, and the European Union. A small text block on the right side of the bottom row states: 'OCEANICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation'.

Climate Coffee

Emmanuele Russo, ETH Zürich

Increasing Intensity of Extreme Heatwaves: The Crucial Role of Metrics

15 February 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET
Online

 OCEANICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

[Bijan Fallah](#) on [Efforts on the Downscaling of CMIP6 Models](#)

22 February 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CET).

Register [here](#).

The poster features the 'Climate Coffee' logo on the left, consisting of four wavy lines in blue, dark blue, light blue, and gold. To the right of the logo, the text 'Climate Coffee' is written in a large, bold, black sans-serif font. Further right is a cluster of dark brown coffee beans. Below the logo and title, the speaker's name 'Bijan Fallah, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK)' is listed. The title of the talk is 'Efforts on the downscaling of CMIP6 models'. The date and time are '22 February 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET' and the format is 'Online'.

Climate Coffee

Bijan Fallah, Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK)

Efforts on the downscaling of CMIP6 models

22 February 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET
Online

[Matthias Röthlisberger](#) on [Quantifying the physical processes leading to atmospheric hot extremes at a global scale](#)

7 March 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CET).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Matthias Röthlisberger, ETH Zürich

**Quantifying the physical processes leading to
atmospheric hot extremes at a global scale**

7 March 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET
Online

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Happening in Winter

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 12-13 February 2024, **Workshop on Anomalous Freshwater for Climate Models**, online
- 18-23 February 2024, [Ocean Sciences Meeting](#), New Orleans

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN:ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

Danish
Meteorological
Institute

**Northumbria
University**
NEWCASTLE

**UNIVERSITY OF
LIVERPOOL**

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